

ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING ANXIETY AND ACHIEVEMENTS AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AT SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN JOLO

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Abstract: This study ascertained the extent and the significant difference between the English language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a second language among Grade 11 students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu during the school year 2017-2018 when data are grouped according to students' gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment. It answered the research questions based on the following hypotheses: 1) There is no significant relationship between English learning and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo; and 2) There is no significant difference in English language learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in JOLO when data are grouped according to gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment. This study employed the descriptive-quantitative research design with 100 Grade 11 students enrolled during School Year 2017-2018. The mean, percentage score and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of students' language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a Second Language, the t-Test for independent samples and One-Way ANOVA were used to determine the significant differences in the students' language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a Second Language.

This study revealed the following findings:

1. On students' demographic profiles; In terms of Negative evaluation communication apprehension and anxiety of English class; In terms of average monthly family income, No significant difference in categories of English language learning anxiety such as gender, out of 100 Grade //students are selected senior high schools in Jolo, Sulu, there are 43 males and 57 females; In terms of average monthly family income, 74% of the students whose family income ranges from 10,000 thousand and below and rest are represented only by with to 8% with 15,000 to 20,000 and 3% with 20, and above; and In terms of parent's educational attainment, those whose parents obtained junior high school and elementary education both obtained 37% each, 24% with college degree, and only 2% with master's degree. None of the student's parents have doctorate degree;
 2. On the extent of students' English language learning anxiety and Achievements; By Students' English language learning anxiety - In terms of negative evaluation; Grade 11 students are rated as with "Moderate Fear" in learning English language; In terms of communication apprehension, students are rated as with
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"Moderate " apprehension in learning English language; In terms offer of test, students are rated as with "Moderate Fear" in learning English language; In terms of anxiety of English class, students are rated as with "Moderate Anxious" in learning English language; By Achievements in terms of their grades, Generally, with the highest grade of 96.00 and 75.00 lowest, students are rated as "Very Satisfactory" in their English language achievement;

3. On the relationship between English language learning anxiety and achievements: Grades and Negative Evaluation, Low correlation; Grades and Communication Apprehension, Nearly zero correlation; Grades and Fear of Test, Nearly zero correlation; Grades and Anxiety of English Class, Nearly zero correlation;

4. 4 On the differences in English language learning anxiety and achievements: On the differences in English language learning anxiety; In terms of gender, except in "fear of test" category, Grade II students significantly differ in learning anxiety in terms of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, fear of and anxiety of English class; In terms of parent's educational attainment, Except in negative evaluation category, no significant difference in communication apprehension, fear of test and anxiety of English class; On the difference in achievements; In terms of gender, No significant difference; In terms of average monthly family income, No significant difference; In terms of parent's educational attainment, NO significant difference. This study concludes that: 1) Majority of the student-respondents come from poor families whose monthly family income ranges from 10,000 thousand and below, whose parents obtained only junior high school and elementary education; 2, Grade 11 students have moderate fear in English language classes; Gender and parent's educational attainment are strong influencing factors than average monthly family income students' level of English language learning anxiety; and This study tend to contradict Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis which accounts for a number of affective variables that play a facilitative, but non-causal, role in second language acquisition, Accordingly, learners with a low level of anxiety are better equipped for success in second language acquisition, vis-à-vis their language achievements. However, in this particular study despite that Grade 11 students are experiencing moderate anxiety level, albeit moderate fear of negative evaluation, moderate communication apprehension, moderate fear of test and moderately anxious of English class still they achieved very satisfactory language performance.

Keywords: Achievement, Communication anxiety, Language learning anxiety, Gender, Test anxiety.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is natural for human being to experience unpleasant emotions, vis-à-vis anxiety when exposed to novel and threatening environment. Internal conflicts, uncertainties and other types of frustrations are, among others' recognized as potential sources of anxiety. In an academic environment, direct and indirect threat to the student's self-esteem and considerable amount of pressure to perform beyond the student's capabilities will produce within him tremendous amount of anxiety. Hence, classroom situations wherein characterized by varied academic and interpersonal activities and performances are nested with students' mixed feelings, albeit anxiety. This is why anxiety has been observed to have bearing on language learner's academic achievement. Horwitz's (2001) study showed that foreign language anxiety has an impact on students' achievement while Phillips (1992) revealed a significant moderate relationship between foreign language anxiety and oral performance in general. Since English is globally accepted as prerequisite to jobs and economic benefits, therefore acquiring English is a must for all Filipinos across curriculum levels. To this effect, in DepEd's senior high school curriculum, the students are expected to develop effective communication skills. But because English must be learned via foreign language context, students enrolled at senior high school who came from the junior high school may or may have not brought with them the necessary language skills, notwithstanding that they are in new learning environment, they are vulnerable to language learning anxiety.

Anxiety is the state or individual when he/she feel, "uneasiness, frustration self-doubt, apprehension, or worry" similar to any other specific anxiety (Scovel, 1978, p. English anxiety can have a debilitating effect and can influence students' adaptation to the Anxiety as and negative emotional reaction argued when or unit a second language". Horwitz et al. (1986) accounts for foreign language anxiety as "a distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom language learning arising from the uniqueness of the language learning process" (p. 128), Guiora et al. (1986) in Horwitz suggest that learning language is itself "a profoundly upsetting psychological proposition", as it threatens the learner's self-concept and world view. However, Wei (2007) has drawn attention to how language learning contexts particularly affect anxiety arousal.

Anxiety is a negative way to present human feelings. When we are anxious, we feel nervous, worried, and fearful. We struggle, tremble, perspire, and our hearts beat quickly. In general, anxiety can be defined as a complex concept dependent upon not only on one's feelings of self-efficacy but also appraisals concerning the potential and perceived threats inherent in certain situations (Tobias, 1986). In simple words, anxiety is usually associated with unpleasant feelings and is similar to fear (Lader, 1975). When communicating in a second language, especially when that language is target environment and ultimately their educational goals. It has been claimed that anxiety is related to performance (Balachandran & Skully, 2004; Tobias & Everson, 1997), and that anxiety has been shown to have a debilitating effect on learning and achievement (Gaudy & Spielberger, 1971; Tobias, 1980). In fact, over the past few years, foreign language educators have strongly argued that anxiety plays a role in Success or failure in the foreign language classroom (Ganschow, et al., 1994). In English language class, student's anxiety may be rooted from communication anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety and English classroom anxiety (Ganschow & Sparks, 1996 in Chun & Wu, 2004). Similarly, Waseem and Jibeen (2013) account for competition, real difficulties in language processing and production, persona/ and interpersonal anxieties and beliefs as multiple factors that cause English language learning anxiety.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to determine the English learning anxiety and achievements among senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu during the school year 2017-2018, specifically, this research answered the following questions, namely:

1. What is the Socio-demographic profile of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender;
 - 1.2. Average monthly family income; and
 - 1.3. Parent's educational attainment?
2. What is the extent of English learning anxiety (Communication anxiety; Fear of negative evaluation; Test anxiety; and English classroom anxiety) and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools?
3. Is there a significant relationship between English learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in JOIO?
4. Is there a significant difference in English learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo when data are grouped according to gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment?

Hypothesis

The following research hypotheses are posited in this study:

- 1) There is no significant relationship between English learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo; and
- 2) There is no significant difference in English language learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo when data are grouped according to gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to achieve the following objectives, namely:

1. To determine the Socio-demographic profile of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu in terms of gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment;
2. To determine the extent of English language learning anxiety and achievement of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu;
3. To find out a degree of correlation between English language learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected Secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu; and

4. To find out a significant difference in English language learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the following model:

1. Krashen (1983) Theory of Second Language Acquisition — Affective Filter

Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis accounts for a number of affective variables that play a facilitative, but non-causal, role in second language acquisition. These variables include: motivation, self-confidence and anxiety. Learners with high motivation, self-confidence, a good self- image, and a low level of anxiety are better equipped for success in second language acquisition. Low motivation, low self-esteem, and debilitating anxiety can combine to raise the affective filter and form a mental block that prevents comprehensible input from being used for acquisition and learning. Although positive affect is necessary, but not sufficient on its own, for acquisition and learning to take place

Conceptual Framework

Based on the above-mentioned model, this particular study is conceptualized as follows-: students' English language learning anxiety is treated as the independent variable while the English language achievement is treated as the dependent variable. The students' demographic profile is treated as the intervening variable. Hence, the interplay of these variables can be illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Model of the Study

Significance of the Study

The results of this study will provide significant contributions to each of the following groups of people:

1. School officials — This study will provide baseline data on students' Perceptions on the English language learning anxiety and summative achievement. This information will serve as point of reference by school officials in the implementation and evaluation of K-12 senior high school curriculum development programs that will directly affect the academic achievements and well-being of senior high school students;

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2. English language teachers — The findings of this study will help English language teachers to determine the ways to determine the social cognitive framework, albeit students' language learning anxiety so that they can best fit and adjust their pedagogical knowledge and skills to the needs of their students; and
3. Researchers in second language learning and teaching — This study will trigger researchers to pursue further avenues or research areas related to this field along the framework of determining individual learner's propensities in second language learning and teaching.

Scope and Delimitation

This study was conducted among the one hundred (100) senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu during School Year 2017-2018. The domain of language learning is delimited to four-factor learning anxiety by Ganschow & Sparks (1996 in Chun & Wu, 2004) communication anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety and English classroom anxiety as well as students' achievement which was based on their first quarter grades in English subject.

Definition of Terms

The following terminologies are hereby operationally defined as they are used in this research:

Gender — refers to the sex of the respondents whether male or female.

Parent's average monthly income — refers to the monthly income of the parents of senior high school students involved as respondents of this study.

Parent's educational attainment — refers to the level of education of the parent whether elementary, high school, college master's or doctorate.

Language learning anxiety — refers to the feeling or uneasiness, frustration, self-doubt, apprehension, or worry by senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu when undertaking communication activities and tasks in English subjects.

Achievement — refers to the first quarter grades of senior high school students in English subject at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu.

Communication anxiety — refers to the communication apprehension in English class of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu.

Fear of negative evaluation — refers to the apprehension of senior high school students about others evaluations, distress over their negative evaluations, and the expectation that others would evaluate them negatively in English classes.

Test anxiety — refers to the unpleasant test experience and unhappy image of senior high students at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu.

English classroom anxiety — refers to the feeling of uneasiness, frustration, self-doubt, apprehension, or worry of senior high school students in English classes at selected secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu.

II. RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter deals with the review of studies and research work related to language learning anxiety that were intended to enhance the theoretical and conceptual framework needed to substantiate the findings of this study.

Foreign Studies

A study closely related to the present research is the one which was conducted by Chan & Wu (2004) on "A Study of Foreign Language Anxiety of EFL Elementary School Students in Taipei County". They argued that different from previous studies on foreign language anxiety which focused on either college or high school level, this study investigated foreign language anxiety of EFL elementary school students in Taiwan. The population of this study was all fifth graders in 205 elementary schools of Taipei County. The researchers used stratified purposeful sampling and cluster sampling to select 18 classes from the total nine educational districts. All the 601 students from the 18 classes were the participants answering the questionnaires. In order to have a further understanding of the students' foreign, language anxiety, 18 high-anxious

students were selected as the interviewees according to their scores in the questionnaires. In addition, all the 9 English teachers were interviewed, too. In this study, questionnaires, interviews, classroom observations, and document collection were applied as instruments. The results were as follows. First, the analysis of the questionnaires showed that the foreign language anxiety tendency of elementary school EFL students was quite obvious. Six variables of English learning experience were found that might affect learners' anxiety level. The result corresponded to that of the previous studies, in which there was a significant negative correlation between foreign language anxiety level and English learning achievement. Second, through a combinatiOnal analysis of multiple data sources, it was found that low proficiency, fear of negative evaluation' Competition of games, anxious personality, and pressure from students themselves and their parents were the five sources of language anxiety. Third, tests, speaking in front of others, spelling, incomprehensible input, and speaking to native speakers were the five anxiety-provoking situations. Fourth, both teachers and students in this study thought that the balance of instructional languages helped lower foreign language anxiety. Finally, the study revealed that teachers' awareness of foreign language anxiety is insufficient. Based on the findings in this study, suggestions of reducing foreign language anxiety were given to teachers, students, and parents. The implications of this exploratory Study include encouraging teachers to enrich their awareness Of foreign language anxiety, carefully dealing with anxiety-provoking situations, encouraging teachers' use of more comprehensible input, encouraging students' participation in additional English activities, encouraging students to share their anxiety experiences, and encouraging parents' involvement in their children's English learning. Based on the findings and implications of this study, students, teachers, and parents can increase their awareness of foreign language anxiety. Accordingly, better ways of dealing with foreign language anxiety can be adopted, and an enjoyable and effective language-learning environment can therefore be developed. Similarly, Anyadubalu (2010) carried out a study on "Self-Efficacy, Anxiety, and Performance in the English Language among Middle-School Students in English Language Program in Satri Si Suriyothai School, Bangkok" which investigated students' perception of self-efficacy and anxiety in acquiring English language, and consequently examined the relationship existing among the independent variables, confounding and students' performances in the English language. The researcher tested the research hypotheses using a Sample group of 318 respondents out of the population size of 400 students. The results obtained revealed that there was a significant moderate negative relationship between English language anxiety and performance in English language, but no significant relationship between self-efficacy and English language performance, among the middle-school students. There was a significant moderate negative relationship between English language anxiety and self-efficacy. It was discovered that general self-efficacy and English language anxiety represented a significantly more powerful set of predictors than the set of confounding variables. Thus, the study concluded that English language anxiety and general self-efficacy were significant predictors of English language performance among middle-school students in Satri Si Suriyothai School. Yang (2012) study on "Language Anxiety: From the Classroom to the Community" claimed that foreign language anxiety has been identified as one of the major factors detrimental to foreign language acquisition and delivery. Much research has focused on language anxiety in classroom environments while relatively little has explored language anxiety in daily social situations. With the consistently high number of Taiwanese students studying in English-speaking countries, it is necessary to gain more Understanding of English communication issues that students encounter in a foreign country. This study examines the underlying constructs of English classroom anxiety and English communication anxiety, and the relationships between language anxiety and selected individual difference variables. The English communication anxiety scale was designed to measure students' English anxiety arising from social interactions. Exploratory factor analyses and multiple regression techniques were used to analyze the data. The results indicate that students' English classroom anxiety primarily falls into two dimensions: communication apprehension and fear of negative evaluation. Students' English communication anxiety falls into three dimensions: social-communication anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety in cross-cultural interactions. The results also reveal that self-perceived English oral proficiency is the most significant predictor of both types of anxiety. Finally, pedagogical implications and recommendations are discussed.

Local Studies

Rochelle Irene Lucas et al. (2011) conducted a study on "English Language Learning Anxiety among Foreign Language Learners in the Philippines" and argued that several researches have revealed that anxiety can hinder success in second or foreign language learning (Bailey, 1 983; Horwitz, Horwitz & Cope, 1986; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1994; Young, 1 991; Ohata, 2005; Pappamihiel, 2002; Williams & Andrade, 2008). It was also found that language learning difficulties could predict anxiety best in foreign language settings (Chen & Chang, 2004). Using Horowitz et al.'s 1986 Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) and Cohen Oxford and Chi's 2001 Language Strategy Survey (I-SS), the proposed study

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intends to investigate the causes of anxiety in English language learning of foreign students in the Philippines. It will also look into the different language strategies utilized by these students who may be experiencing anxieties in learning the English language. Specifically, the study would like to target foreign students studying in tertiary institutions in Manila where these students abound. Findings suggest that these type of learners used vocabulary strategy to efficiently learn the English language and to cope with their English class anxiety. It has been found that the employment of this strategy enables the learners to take charge of their own learning as this serves as their basic aid to learn other macro skills in the target language.

III. METHOD: RESEARCH BLUEPRINT

This chapter deals with the research method to be adopted in the conduct of this study. It also deals with research design, locale, and respondents of the study, sampling design, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatments of data.

Research Design

Bless and Higson-Smith (1995A) defined research design as “a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts (p.63). Similarly, Babbie and Mouton (2001, p.75) regard research design as the road map or blueprint by which one intends to conduct a research and achieve his/her research goals and objectives.” A descriptive research design via a quantitative research method was employed in this study, that is, with purport to describe, quantify, and infer the phenomenon of students’ perceptions of English language learning anxiety, and the significant difference in these perceptions when data are grouped according to gender, parent’s average monthly income and parent’s educational attainment.

Students at selected senior high schools in Jolo were the main source of data which were quantified and treated with appropriate statistical tools to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet research were the sources of information that were used as bases to structured and enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research. Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope’s (1986) Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) was the main instrument used in collecting data from the respondents. Student’s grades in English were obtained during the first quarter (First Grading) which served as the basis for their achievement in English.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the town of Jolo specifically among selected senior high schools in Jolo, Sulu during the School Year 2017-2018. Jolo is the capital town of Sulu province where these selected senior high schools are located. These senior high schools are under the direct supervision of DepEd-Sulu through the leadership of the principal, head teacher and teacher-in-charge.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the students at selected senior high schools in Jolo, Sulu. Specifically, respondents that were included in this study are grade 11 students. At least one hundred (100) students with 50 males and 50 females as representative samples from each of the selected senior high schools that were utilized in this study. The table below shows the distribution of samples of this study.

Distribution of samples according to Schools and Gender

Schools	Grade 11 Students		Total
	Gender		
	Male	Female	
MSU-Senior High	10	10	20
Jolo School of Agriculture	10	10	20
Jolo School of Fisheries	10	10	20
SSC-Senior High School	10	10	20
Sulu High School	10	10	20
Total	50	50	100

Sampling Design

A non-probability sampling method through purposive sampling procedure was employed in this study. That is, due to access, availability and time constraints, representative samples from MSU-Senior High; Jolo School of Agriculture; Jolo School of Fisheries; SSC-Senior High School; and Sulu High School were chosen purposively as samples of this study. The use of purposive sampling procedure will ensure the collection of desired quality and quantity of data that were used in this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, the following steps were applied:

- 1) A permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College and then from the school administrators such as College President; Chancellor, DepEd-Sulu division superintendent, principals, head teachers and teacher-in-charge of the selected senior high schools in Jolo; and
- 2) The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were conducted personally by the researcher,

Research Instrument

A self-report questionnaire was the main instrument used to gather data on demographic profiles, students' perceptions on English language learning anxiety at selected senior high schools in Jolo, Sulu. Horwitz, Horwitz, and Copes (1986) Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) which was used to investigate students' foreign language anxiety in English learning was utilized for this study.

In the FLCAS, there are 33 items, and a 5-point scale ranging from "strongly agree" (5 points) to "Strongly disagree" (1 point). Each anxiety score will be gained by summing the ratings of the thirty-three items. The higher the total points will be, the more anxious the student is.

The theoretical framework consists of the three components: communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. The items were developed from student's self-reports who were concerned about their foreign language classes, from clinical experience where the first author has long experience in dealing with anxious students in her own foreign language classes, and from a review of related instruments. The scale has 33 items scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree".

The four factor FCLAS scale used for the present study (Zhao, 2007), originally developed by Horwitz et al., (1986), to measure English learning anxiety of the respondents. Although Cao's (2011) study revealed the three factor scale to be a better fit for investigating anxiety of second language learning, the present researcher felt that the four factor model is more appropriate to be used in the Philippine context. Having 'anxiety of English classes' as the fourth factor, it would afford a more holistic understanding of the situation as learners of English in the Philippines are the products of a differentiated system of education and the ones coming from the Tausug medium would be suffering from classroom anxiety as compared to those who would have had an English medium education. The four factor scale was used by Zhao (2007) to measure the anxiety of Chinese English learners and Wassem & Jibeen (2013) on Pakistani students. The scale is composed of 33 items, measured on the five point Likert

Scales, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, along the value of 1-5. The higher the score the more effective it is of the anxiety the learners feel in the English class. Items 2, 5, 8, 11, 14, 18, 22, 28, 32 were inversely coded. The scale is composed of four subscales. Items 3, 7, 13, 15, 20, 23, 25, 31, and 33 measure feel of negative evaluation (Horwitz et al., 1986), items 1, 9, 14, 18, 24, 27, 29, and 32 measure communication apprehension (Horwitz et al., 1986), and items 2, 8, 10, 19, and 21 measure fear of tests (Horwitz et al., 1986), while item 4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 16, 17, 22, 26, 28, 30 measured anxiety of English classes (Zhao, 2007 in Wassem & Jibeen, 2013). Cronbach's alpha for total FLCAS or total anxiety scale in Wassem & Jibeen (2013) was .92.

Validity and Reliability

The instrument used in this research was patterned and adapted from The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) which was originally developed by Horwitz et al. (1986). This standardized questionnaire was already used by

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Zhao 2007, to measure the anxiety of Chinese English learners and Wassem & Jibeen (2013 on Pakistani students. Thus, its validity and reliability are already established. However, to suit its applicability with the present study, this was subjected for perusal of at least two experts from among the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed in the treatments of data that were gathered for this study, namely:

- 1) Mean, percentages and standard deviation were employed to determine the following: the socio-demographic profiles of students in terms of gender, average monthly family income and parent’s educational attainment;
- 2) T-test for independent samples was employed to determine the significant differences in students’ perceptions on English language learning anxiety when data are grouped according to gender; and
- 3) One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in students’ perceptions on English language learning anxiety when data are grouped according to average monthly family income and parent’s educational attainment.

Scoring of responses

The following ranges and verbal interpretations were used to score the responses in the items of the questionnaire.

- a) Five (5-choices) Likert-scales

Options	Scale Range	Verbal Interpretations Under Four Factors			
		Communication Apprehension	Negative Evaluation	Fear of Test	English Class Anxiety
5	4.50 – 5.00	Very High	Very Strong Fear	Very Strong Fear	Very Highly Anxious
4	3.50 – 4.49	High	Strong Fear	Strong Fear	Highly Anxious
3	2.50 – 2.49	Moderate	Moderate Fear	Moderate Fear	Moderately Anxious
2	1.50 – 2.49	Low	Low Fear	Low Fear	:Low Anxious
1	1.00 – 1.49	Little	Little Fear	Little Fear	Little Anxious

- a) Scales for English Achievement

Scales	Grading Scale	Scale Range	Description
5	90 – 100	4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding
4	85 – 89	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory
3	80 – 84	2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory
2	75 – 79	1.50 – 2.49	Fairly Satisfactory
1	74 & below	1.00 – 1.49	Failure

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data obtained for this study. Specifically, it also presents the students’ socio-demographic profiles in terms of gender, average monthly family income and parent’s educational attainment: the extent of students’ achievement and learning anxiety towards learning English as a second language; and the significant differences in students’ achievement and learning anxiety towards learning English as a second language when data are grouped according to students’ socio-demographic profiles.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter deals with the summary findings, conclusions and recommendations based on proper computation and thorough analyses of data gathered for this study.

Summary

This study geared to ascertain the extent and the significant difference between the English language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a second language among Grade 11 students at selected secondary schools in Job, Sulu during the school year 2017-2018 when data are grouped according to students' gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment.

This study answered the research questions based on the following hypotheses: 1) There is no significant relationship between English learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo; and 2) There is no significant difference in English language learning anxiety and achievements of senior high school students at selected secondary schools in Jolo when data are grouped according to gender, average monthly family income and parent's educational attainment.

This study employed the descriptive-quantitative research design with 100 Grade 11 students enrolled during School Year 2017-2018. The mean, percentage score and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of students' language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a Second Language. The t-Test for independent samples and One-Way ANOVA were used to determine the significant differences in the students' language learning anxiety and achievements towards learning English as a Second Language.

Findings

This Study revealed the following findings:

1. On students' demographic profiles

1.1. In terms of gender, that out of 100 Grade 11 students at selected senior high schools in Jolo, Sulu, there are 43% males and 57% females.

1.2. In terms of average monthly family income, out of 100 Grade 11 students, 74% whose family income ranges from 10,000 thousand and below. The rest are represented only by 15% with 10,000 to 15,000; 8% with 15,000 to 20,000 and 3% with 20,000 and above.

1.3. In terms of parent's educational attainment, out of 100 Grade 11 students, those whose parents obtained junior high school and elementary education both obtained 37% each, 24% with college degree, and only 2% with master's degree. None of the student's parents have doctorate degree.

2. On the extent of students' English language learning anxiety and Achievements

2.1. By Students English language learning anxiety

2.1.1 In terms of fear of negative evaluation: Grade 11 students are related as with "Moderate Fear" in learning English language.

2.1.2 In terms of communication apprehension: Grade 11 students are related as with "Moderate apprehension" in learning English language.

2.1.3 In terms of fear of test: Grade 11 students are related as with "Moderate Fear" in learning English language.

2.1.4. In terms of anxiety of English class; Grade 11 students are rated as with "Moderate Anxious" in learning English language.

2.2. By Achievements: Grade 11 students in terms of their grades, generally, with the highest grade of 96.00 and 75.00 lowest, the respondents are rated as "Very Satisfactory" in their English language achievement.

3. On the relationship between English language learning anxiety and achievements

3.1 Grades and Negative Evaluation: Low correlation

3.2 Grades and Communication Apprehension: Nearly zero correlation

3.3. Grades and Fear of Test: Nearly zero correlation

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3.4. Grades and Anxiety of English Class: Nearly zero correlation

4. On the differences in English language learning anxiety and achievements

4.1. On the differences in English language learning anxiety

4.1.1. In terms of gender: Except in “fear of test” category. Grade 11 students significantly differ in learning anxiety in terms of negative evaluation, communication apprehension and anxiety of English class.

4.1.2 In terms of average monthly family income: No significant difference in categories of English language learning anxiety such as negative evaluation communication apprehensions fear of test and anxiety of English class.

4.1.3. In terms of parent’s educational attainment: Except in negative evaluation category, no significant difference in communication apprehension, fear of test and anxiety of English class.

4.2 On the differences in achievements

4.2.1. In terms of gender; No significant difference

4.2.2 In terms of average monthly family income; No significant difference

4.2.3. in terms of parent’s educational attainment; No significant difference

Conclusion

The following are the conclusions made based of the findings of this study: Majority of the student-respondents come from poor families whose monthly family income ranges from 10,000 thousand and below, whose parents obtained only senior high school and elementary education.

2. Generally, Grade 11 students have moderate fear in English language classes.

3. Gender and parent’s educational attainment are strong influencing factors than average monthly family income on students’ level of English language learning anxiety.

4. Results of this study tend to contradict Krashen’s Affective Filter Hypothesis which accounts for a number of affective variables that play a facilitative, but non-causal, role in second language acquisition. Accordingly, learners with a low level of anxiety are better equipped for success in second language acquisition. vis-à-vis their language achievements. However, in this particular study despite that Grade II students are experiencing moderate anxiety level, albeit moderate fear of negative evaluation, moderate communication apprehension. moderate fear of test and moderately anxious of

English class still they achieved very satisfactory language performance.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings and conclusions, the following conclusions are hereby forwarded in this study:

1. English language teachers at senior high schools should manifest cognizance, consider extra care and mindfulness in promoting students’ awareness towards language learning process since male and female students differ in anxiety;

2. Considering their socio-economic status, parents should be well-oriented with the nature of senior high school curriculum so that they can be actively involved in providing socio-cognitive learning support for their children;

3. Social and academic organizations like language club should be organized and established so that students can be provided the opportunities to overcome their fear. Hesitations and confusions towards developing English language skills;

4. Teachers should introduce “a paradigm shifts”, that is they should motivate students to struggle and change their mentality from believing that poverty and parent’s low educational background are hindrances to the development of their language proficiency;

5. The school administrator must provide the necessary support to English language teachers through trainings and seminars in order to update their pedagogical knowledge and skills relevant to the implementation of the present curriculum;

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7. The school heads should work with the teachers and parents to lessen the diverse effects of some socio-affective factors, vis-à-vis English anxiety that affects the

English language instruction; and

8. Researchers in the field of education are encouraged to conduct similar study but to include variables like motivation, learning styles, learning strategies and problems in some other settings. This is suggested to constantly evolve research in education that would lead to the enhancement of teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills.

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